

**Title: STRATEGIC SUPPLY CHANGE AND LOGISTICS
MANAGEMENT (Starbucks a case study)**

By

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Starbucks for half a century has ballooned to a large multinational coffee brand. With over 346, 000 human resource, it stands as a major employer of labor. The coffee giant has a considerably effective human resource management practice that not only aligns with its business model and company culture but also invests in their employees to bring out the best in them while maintaining company culture, values and vision. The effectiveness of its human resource management is showcased by the challenges such as market fluctuations, competition and staff turnovers it can overcome. To dissect the international plans of Starbucks into its multidimensional facets, leadership theories are analyzed, and the contingency theory of leadership selected as the most suitable to Starbucks international plans. A powerful reason among others is the flexibility it affords the company as it tries to integrate its varying human resource across cultural lines.

Pursuant to an analysis of the leadership styles extrapolated from the contingency theory, the challenges that could be incurred from an internationalization of Starbucks are within the spheres of cultural differences, economic variation, technology divide and legal framework. In analyzing these challenges, one could conclude that in order to control the influences of behavior on the international human resource management, there is a need to deploy best practices of resource management. Starbucks has a decent and effective human resource management, but understanding the strengths of MacDonald's human resource management vis-à-vis its Hamburger University - could be considered an industrial standard that could help restaurant chains maintain company culture and attain their vision.

1.0.

INTRODUCTION

Starbucks corporation is a multinational chain of coffee based restaurants that also sells a range of other fast foods - (Non - coffee drinks, baked goods and snacks). It is currently the world's largest coffee store chain and the fastest growing coffee chain, with over 30000 stores in over 70 countries. Founded 1971 in Seattle, Washington, where its headquarters is situated, the corporation comprises several subsidiaries operating with different names that may have a 'Starbucks' attached to it or not. It also has an entertainment section which markets and sells films, books and music in the locality where they are being guided by the season at a particular time in order to take care of the need of its customers. The company has been expanding rapidly locally and globally majorly because of its human resources management practices guided by its mission and vision thus;

Starbucks' mission strongly upholds humanity, and that guides their decisions in ensuring that every step they take is all about the well-being of their employees, customers, stakeholders and neighborhood and that has led to the success witnessed in their local and global expansion. In the 1990s Starbucks opened a new store every working day locally in the US and after launching its first global store in Canada, it started opening stores in other countries, this expansion was to consolidate their market and operations but was not without issues which revolved around anti-competitive practices.

The coffee giant prides itself with its over 346 000 employees around the world. The fact that this employees are from different countries and cultures that possess differing labor laws and economic states. To cover all these employees under one company human resource plan would be quite challenging considering their status and culture, thus a general idea of Starbucks human resource management practices cannot be done without considering the differing nature of human resource practices.

Noteworthy is the fact that Starbucks also operates on a pseudo franchising model termed licensing. According to Franchise (2020), Starbucks is not a franchise; one can only open a Starbucks as a license owner. The coffee giant prefers licensing to keep control over the stores and the product's quality.

Noe et al (2010) described Starbucks as a company that embraces diversity, provides medical care, vacation, retirement plans and more for their employees. These benefits are intended to increase motivation, recognition and retention as enshrined in their resource management practices.

This report aims at analyzing the human resource management practices strategies / processes adopted by Starbucks in their international expansion that contributed immensely to the success witnessed so far in these expansions both locally and internationally which will stand as a guide for future international expansion. It will showcase how these practices enabled the company achieve their objectives because human resource is plays a very vital role in the achievement of a company's goals and objectives.

Over the years, from inception, Starbucks is known to introduce good human resource management strategies to improve its market and operations and so its human resources department is designed and equipped to attract best/talent in the industry and also has a training division that trains all employees on their adopted best practices. Starbucks has a mentoring program that gets the seniors to mentor the juniors and also employees who have undergone master coffee courses wear black apron in order to differentiate the different expertise in their fields of endeavor.

Stores
Worldwide

dadaviz.com

Fig 1. Starbucks stores global representation on domination

Fig 1.2 - Starbucks growth in number of stores

2.0. STARBUCKS HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

Over the years, research and findings have proved that employees are the most important assets for the overall growth of the company's growth. Starbucks do not take tightly this fact and so has adopted the strategy that projects their employees as the backbone of their successful operations. Starbucks therefore provides its employees with environment that facilitates faster growth in comparison with other competitors. This is the reason behind the implementation of its human resource management practices and processes as strategy for attaining a competitive height over its competitors within the retail industry in the global market. The company therefore strives to attract best hands and retain them after training. Starbucks is known to have developed a warm relationship between employees and customers towards the ease of achievement of its goals. The HRM stakeholders affected by operation and market practices are well taken care of by Starbucks. These are customers who expect better products and services, employees who expect attractive job with very good compensation, shareholders who expect return on the money they invested and communities who expect activities that will positively affect them as well as minimize harmful hazards to their environment.

From the business model of Starbucks, These HRM stakeholders are major consideration in their strategies. This position is well acknowledged by Starbucks human resource: through training efforts as well as its work-life balance which it offers its employees. According to Kelly, S.M (2018), the five areas of Human Resource Management include: recruitment, training, employee benefits, labor relations and risk management.

3a (i) critically review the existing HRM practices of your organization.

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AT STARBUCKS

“If you want 10 days of happiness, grow grain. If you want 10 years of happiness grow a tree. If you want 100 years of happiness, grow people.”- Harvey Mackay.

Starbucks is known as talent power house because it focuses on hiring great people who helps the company achieve the tremendous success it has recorded over the years and it achieves this through an extensive recruitment and training program and this has made them achieve a competitive edge from its competitors.

For some years now, Starbucks has won awards as the best company to work in - Fortune magazine placed it as best company to work as an employee for some years now. It's known as a value driven company with strong rules/principles that has guided their HRM. It places value on their employees and so invests heavily on them for best result. Starbucks has created an atmosphere around the company that makes employees feel respected and proud to be part of the company because of the believe that if they place partners first then they will put in their best towards productivity, customer satisfaction and subsequently lead to the achievement of the company's goals/objectives.

Working Culture in the Organization.

“The relationship we have with our people and the culture of our company is our most sustainable competitive advantage.”-Howard Schulz, chairman and chief global strategist of Starbucks 2002.

Fig 2.1 - Starbucks corporate responsibility. Starbucks, (2011).

Starbucks culture was built on career growth of employees and strong open communication. This the company does by holding several open forums in a year where the update employees about the state of the company in terms of growth. There is company newsletter published regularly which discloses developments within and around the company with column on benefits and ownership program for employees. It creates several employee friendly policies and work culture that supports them. It provides serene work environment and treats every employee with so much dignity and respect. Their main focus is first of all to attract best employees in the industry then offer them extensive education and training opportunities. Their HRM team engages employees in order to get them loyal to the brand because they believe that the employees represent their product brand. Given their vision statement, employees has been part of their short and long term goals of the company.

Working at Starbucks

- **Be a Partner:**
 - Competitive Pay
 - Insurance: medical, dental, life...
 - Bonuses
 - Paid time off
 - Retirement saving plan
 - Stock option and discounted stock purchase plan
 - Emergency financial aid
 - A free pound of coffee each weeks
- **Retail positions:**
 - Baristas
 - Shift Supervisors
- **Management position:**
 - Assistant store manager
 - Store manager
 - District manager
 - Regional Director
- **Professional Services Careers:**
 - Engineering
 - Finance
 - Legal
 - Marketing
 - Operations
 - Quality
 - Communications
 - Call Center

A latte to think.

got milk?

June 1, 2011 17

Figure 2.2 - Human resource at Starbucks - Starbucks (2020)

Recruitment

“We are not in the coffee business serving people, we’re in the people business serving coffee”- Howard Schultz Starbucks (CEO)

Starbucks policy is to have the right people recruit the right work force. They advertise for vacancies through job fairs, company website, in-store adverts and word of mouth in order to select suitable candidate for any given vacancy. Their strategy is first of all look for coffee lovers. In a nutshell, the company makes use of different avenues in their recruitment exercise like walk-in, referral etc. The company adopts the principle of advertising the kind of candidate they are looking for and state it categorically on their website, this exercise is known as self-selection method with emphasis on adaptability, dependability and passionate team players.

Starbucks recruitment approach has been described by Mark (2019) as a thorough process. The interviews are simple but the screening process is complicated. Potential

candidates are screened to ascertain the type of cultural background he/she has in order to determine whether it will have positive or negative impact on the organization as well as check for relevant experience possesses

Starbucks engages the services of enterprise staffing management software in maintaining their hundreds of thousands of database of candidates that have gone through job application exercise and taken some basic oral interviews which are informational and skills based, with this, it's easy for Starbucks to swiftly and systematically screen out unqualified candidates and recruits suitably for stores.

Their recruitment and selection processes goes through rigorous interview which seek to bring out the core skills of the candidate relevant to the job available after which two rounds of interviews based on behavioral follows.

Given their mission, Starbucks from onset set out to recruit right in order to keep the line of communication open throughout the organization and also reward while striving to retain employees with higher salary than minimum salary. Very attractive allowances are provided for employees as well as robust medical health care which extend to spouses.

Their medical package covers comprehensively like vision, dental, vacation, stock option, tuition reimbursement and much more. They create rewards for employees as often as possible in order to retain them for better productivity.

Consequently a panel made up of managers is set up with various managers at different locations to interview prospective employees. This whole process of recruitment can take up to 3 weeks. This

thorough recruitment exercise ensures that every new employee adjusts to the job role with so much passion that will drive selfless services to customers. door reviews (Glassdoor, 2020) reveals an 80% positive recruitment experience with the flexibility of having an online interview which boasts a 70% of all recruitment.

Starbucks sells experience not just coffee and the experience is holistically dependent on the attitudes, ability and capability of the employees in their frontline who interface with over 30 million customers globally every week.

Training

“Treat people like family, and they will be loyal and give their all.” Howard Schultz Starbucks CEO

Starbucks has an extensive internal training for her employees as it nurtures the personality and skills of the employee. Their recruitment exercise is a typical Tell, Show and Do process according to Fowler (2018) where the new recruit takes time watching their coaches serve customers or engage in doing it themselves. Starbucks engages them in a 24 hour in house classroom learning where they are trained on the company’s ethics, values, mission and vision in order to get the best from them thereby increase productivity as well as reduce employee turnover. The regular practice is continuous learning/training for both new recruits and long serving employees on better ways to serve customers in order to get their loyalty. The company invests heavily on employee training both internal and external in order to meet up the requirement of the industry and remain highly competitive which is why they remain the fastest growing beverage company in the world.

Employee Developing

Learning & Development

- **Starbucks Experience** – To learn about the origins of Starbucks, and its corporate culture.
- **Core 1 & 2** – To learn the technical skills to be a successful Barista
- **Supervisor Programme** – For those who want to have a leadership role.
- **Retail Manager in Training** – To set partners up for success in running their own Starbucks store
- **District Manager Training** – To broaden the knowledge of a population
- **Plus** - A wide range of management development opportunities, including topics such as leadership, coaching and influencing

October 3, 2006

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Figure 2.3. - Employee development at Starbucks - Starbucks (2020)

In Starbucks every new employee is engaged with a 24-hour paid training module known as “First Impression”. This is a curriculum developed by the HRM of Starbucks on all that a new recruit needs to know about the company to excel and is taught by the store managers, about their products, knowledge, and creation of a positive customer experience. This curriculum is constantly updated by a 32-member select team of highly experienced and skilled training specialists with store managers in order to ensure consistency and effective training throughout the organization. Also, managers and assistant store managers are made to take up a 10-week retail management course, computer, leadership, and product knowledge classes as well as training on diversity.

After the first impression training, follows two-week barista training which offers the first-hand training for new recruits on the required skills and knowledge at Starbucks’ prestigious coffee company by using simple tools to teach skills through one-on-one delivery and on-the-job training,

then after this follows two week module. At completion of these trainings, employees are issued with certificate of completion of this requirement as a prove of qualification to be fully engaged in the system. In all of these the company engages employees in frequent external programs and seminars that will improve their skills. These trainings help in changing certain negative behavioral attitudes in employees for better output as well as build certain skills required for the enhancement of productivity like enhancing self-esteem, listening skills, acknowledgement of customers.

Figure 2.4. - The 5 'Be's' skills of Starbucks employee - Starbucks (2020)

The lengths of time which different levels are engaged in training processes depends on the positions and are designed to give partners that are not in the front-line true experience making beverages and interacting with customers.

Benefits to Employees.

Starbucks world class benefits and programs for their partners are borne out of the quest to satisfy their needs. Total reward package include basic pay and bonus, retirement savings as well as stocks. The company appreciates respects and includes different kinds of people as well as embrace diversity a great deal. Starbucks offers success pan and life retirement package for every employee because they believe that the success of their employee is ultimately the company's success.

Interactivity within employees: HR managers are responsible for conducting activities, events and celebrations in the organisation which gives way to team building opportunities. Moreover, it enhances interactivity within employees and instills a sense of trust and respect among peers. For many years Starbucks's has conducted annual surveys to receive feedback from crew, managers and corporate employees. In 2011 Starbucks began to improve the way in which they measure how much their employees enjoy working at the company and in future they portend to be asking for that feedback on a more regular basis and in different formats. In addition to the annual surveys other measures are in the place to receive employee feedback and track their employees performance including:

- I. A quarterly People scorecard which includes a range of metrics such as proportion of female employees, annual leave balances, turnover and number of unscheduled absences.
- II. Brown Bag Lunches which are hosted by a member of the leadership team each month. A random selection of corporate employees is invited to have lunch with a member of the leadership team, who facilitates a small group discussion. Feedback and actions are shared with attendees.
- III. Anonymous exit surveys.
- IV. Announced and unannounced audits of restaurant compliance with employment legislation, policies and procedures.

Conflict management: The department to go to when any kind of professional conflict arises between employees is HR. They ensure that issues and conflicts are resolved effectively, approaching the problem with an unbiased attitude and encouraging effective communication to reach a solution. In addition, they help employees understand various ways of developing effective work relationships and the importance of not letting personal judgement affect their behaviour. At Starbucks 93% of crew said they enjoy the friendships they have at work. Thus HR can be said to be creating a positive impact.

Establishing a healthy work culture: A healthy work culture is pivotal in bringing out the best in employees. HR managers contribute significantly in setting up a healthy and friendly work culture, which further translates into better productivity among employees.

Compliance: HR professionals work towards making the organisation compliant with employment laws, as well as maintaining records of hiring processes and applicants' log.

ii. Analyse the importance of HRM and its practices in your organisation with specific focus on how it helps in overcoming business issues/ challenges for better performance.

3.0. IMPORTANCE OF HRM AND ITS PRACTICES IN STARBUCKS

HR management helps bridge the gap between employees' performance and the organizational strategic objectives. Therefore, an efficient and effective HR management team takes the company above its competition. According to statistics released by SilkRoad, 53% of HR professionals believe that employee engagement increases when the on boarding process is better.

CultureIQ released statistics stating that 73% of employers believe that a healthy corporate culture gives their firm a competitive advantage. Furthermore, according to a survey conducted by SHRM, 89% of HR leaders confirmed that ongoing peer feedback has a positive influence on the organization.

Human resource operations contribute significantly to the success of an organization. At Starbucks, the role of Human resource is a very important aspect of their operations such that under the direction of four key executives of Starbucks (Howard Schultz, Dave Olsen, Howard Behar and Orin Smith) in 1990 drafted its first mission statement and the first was to, "Provide a great work environment and to treat each other with respect and dignity." And as years go by, additional executives were added to human resource. Leadership is the core element of business process of Starbucks which ensures that the organizational culture is maintained by every successor CEO and this has contributed to Starbucks exponential growth over the years. Starbucks HRM practices is so important that it has helped in overcoming the business challenges of Starbucks for better

productivity as can be seen in the various ways they used their HRM practices to overcome their challenges thus;

3.1 STRATEGIC ISSUES FACING STARBUCKS AND HOW THEIR HRM PRACTICE HAS HELPED IN OVERCOMING IT

The current global financial crisis is forcing Starbucks to close many stores around the world but with the well positioning of Starbucks HRM which primarily recruit and train right people at the right time as well as treat the employees with so much respect and dignity even as they train them internally and externally to become loyal to the company's wish. Given this imminent closure of stores, Starbucks has been able to swiftly move into more of delivery in order to meet up and still retain customers with the loyalty of the employees, they are able to go through this challenge and collectively proffer solution having been made to see themselves as part of the company.

Competition is another challenge Starbucks is dealing with as there are so many coffee shops all over the world and they still need to stand out in the midst stiff completion and this Starbucks is able to achieve given their strategic HRM practices. Even though there is serious concern about how long consumers will stick with Starbucks before moving over to any of the competitors like Dunkin Donuts, Mcdonald's, Costa coffee and Caffe Nero in UK but Starbucks has been able to retain and attract more consumers using one of its HRM practice of creating a conducive atmosphere for the consumers and employees and so the stores have become popular place for casual meetings or study while drinking coffee with free Wifi and their well trained personnel are always abreast with the

trend with the competitors which they use for forecast and recommendation on best well to continue to take the lead.

Also Starbucks continuously uses its innovation strategy on retaining consumers by establishing brand presence and value like the creation of Reserve Roastery and Tasting Room Stores where highly esteemed consumers will be given world class treatment by well trained personnel where an interactive experience with baristas will be established. Starbucks reward/benefit program has contributed immensely to solving this challenge as the satisfied personnel are committed to ensuring the consumers have wonderful experience whenever they visit any of the Starbucks stores. Starbucks has consistently seen its reward program grow despite whatever may be the change. Even though some consumers will be lost to competitors, that will be insignificant since their HRM practice of strategies of reward program overtime has resulted to more customer retention and more customer acquisition.

Increase in prices of coffee bean

Prices of coffee fluctuates but has been on continuous increase for some time now. This being as a result of drought in Brazil and Vietnam*largest producers of coffee). Since Starbucks started collecting data about the coffee inventory in 1995, the company has recorded a consecutive reduction in coffee bean for the past 12 quarters, this being the longest ever as a result of this coffee prices has skyrocketed and because coffee bean is the main raw material, this increment and supply shortage affects Starbucks margins negatively. In this regard, Starbucks has effectively used its strategic HRM to pass on this increase to her customers. So the highly priced Starbucks coffee has been accepted by its consumers because of its HRM practice of their corporate culture (Be welcoming, Be Considerate, Be knowledgeable, Be genuine, Be Involved)

Inadequate Marketing Strategy of Starbucks on Advertising

This poses some hindrances in the growth opportunities of Starbucks. They rather build their brand image by promoting their drink cup-by-cup with customers. This they do by their emphasis on getting the walk in customer to have a cup and that ends thereby reducing their chances of attracting valuable customers in the market place. Their not pushing for their products to be distributed in the supermarket because of their concern about adulteration if packaged into plastic bags has left them with only walk in customers who bring more people by word of mouth based on their experience in the store.

Starbucks has been able to overcome this challenge by the addictive nature of their products which their HRM practice helped in achieving by placing quality above quantity and customer and employee special treatment with respect and dignity which in turn retains and attracts more by word of mouth irrespective of the high price.

Keeping up with market trends: This challenge is very critical especially in this age of innovations and technological know-how of better ways to do business in order to meet the ever changing demands of consumers, For Starbucks to remain competitive, it must keep abreast of changes in taste and swift delivery demands of consumers amongst others. A comprehensive analysis of existing trends and the viability of similar restaurant ventures in the community is a good way to forecast potential revenue in each quarter. In solving this challenge Starbucks Strategy management proffers the solution. This it does by playing a very vital role in human resource management. HR managers manage strategies to ensure the organization reaches its business goals, as well as contributing significantly to the corporate decision-making process, which includes assessments for current employees and predictions for future ones based on business demands. In the case of Starbucks this is practically useful in keeping up with market trends. Getting new talents to constantly improve Starbucks is a priority of its human resource management practice.

Global Expansion Strategy

Starbucks follows a rigorous expansion strategy which is capable of taking a toll on their brand. With the growth experienced by Starbucks, there is a tendency to focus on increasing output and locations and less on brand and quality. Starbucks has remained committed to their HRM practice of learning and development which has kept them successful all the way.

Risk of non-franchising

Starbucks policy of non-franchising is a great challenge because they single handedly take up the whole risk embedded in the business. This challenge has been curbed with Starbucks HRM practice of extensive training both internal and external where new employees and existing ones are made to go through thorough training about the business based on practice done by coach who has been on the job thus closing every possible gap with his experience and knowledge.

Effective inventory management and menu pricing

Restaurants usually keep a keen focus on managing expenses. One crucial component of keeping costs low is effectively managing inventory. Management of Franchises who fail to do so may face unforeseen expenditures and supply overages or shortages throughout peak business periods. Thus comprehensive training on best management practices to the human resource deployed to these franchises must be done effectively. This, Starbucks does by its extensive Training and development programs for the new recruits and existing ones thus eliminating every possible wastage thereby improving productivity.

Hiring permanent and seasonal/contract staff

Having the right employees is one of the secrets of successful restaurants. Starbucks always on toes about recruiting the right personnel at the right time to ensure a good team is in place during all seasons especially during times of the year where customer volume increases such as summer time. Placing greater emphasis on finding and training staff can reduce costs over time and enhance customer service - two significant priorities for Starbucks. Starbucks HRM practices work towards reducing costs, such as with recruitment and retention. Their HR professionals are trained to conduct efficient negotiations with potential and existing employees, as well as being well-versed with employee benefits that are likely to attract quality candidates and retaining the existing workforce. Keeping abreast with employees needs is one such way Starbucks HR management does this. As reported in 2.0, Starbucks's employment comes with certain benefits.

3b. Review of leadership theories

- i. Critically review any two theories of leadership (trait, behavioural, contingency).
[5 marks]
- ii. Assess the suitability of one of the leadership theory that you have analysed in the context of your organization's international plans. The analysis should include a careful consideration and justification of the factors determining the chosen leadership style.

3.2. LEADERSHIP THEORIES

Figure 3.0 - Leadership theories - Kendra, C. and Morin, A. (2019)

Leadership theories are schools of thought brought forward to explain how and why certain individuals become leaders. The theories emphasize the traits and behaviors that individuals can adopt to boost their own leadership abilities. Early studies on the psychology of leadership pointed to the fact that leadership skills are inherent abilities that people are born with. It was not until recently that formal leadership theories emerged, despite leadership becoming a concept of interest at the beginning of time.

For the purposes of this paper, two out of the eight major leadership theories will be discussed and these are: The trait theory of leadership and the contingency leadership theory.

The Trait Theory Of Leadership

This Trait theory of leadership identifies different personality traits and characteristics that are easily linked to leadership success noticed across various situations. The proponents are of the opinion that leaders are born not made. History is shaped by extraordinary leaders according to Carlyle. He believed that leadership cannot be developed and this inspired early researchers and made them focused mainly on inheritable traits. This is borne out of the following rationale;

- That certain trait produces certain behavioural pattern.
- Considering certain situations, patterns noticed to be consistent.
- Leadership traits are not developed but are created with people.

Figure 3.3 - Trait Leadership - Carlyle (2020)

This is an attempt to answer why some people are good leaders while some are not. This theory propounded that the natural leaders after being identified are nurtured to become great leaders.

Ever since this theory was published, psychologists have analyzed and argued this theory. From 1940s and 1970s, Ralph Melvin Stogdill said that leadership is the outcome of the interaction between the individual and the given situation and not just a predefined traits. By 1980s James M.

Kouzes and Barry Z. Posner said that credibility was key in identifying a good leader among other things.

Leadership Traits

According to researchers, traits commonly identified among leaders include but not limited to the following;

- Motivator
- Flexible and adaptable
- Courageous
- Innovator
- Fearless
- Willingness to accept Responsibility
- Stability
- Smart
- Result oriented
- Perseverance
- Interpersonal Skill
- Trustworthy
- Self Confidence

- Understanding

This theory has a lot of criticism from researchers and psychologists given the findings gotten from surveys made across different facets of successful leadership globally. Findings show that some great leaders became one after going through some developmental/training processes while some who had the traits who were nurtured couldn't make great leadership because leadership is more about training/developmental rather than inheritance. It's been proven that most of those who possess the traits never became leaders and those that did make it to that position, never became great leaders. This is because the situation that arose that made him a leader can disappear after sometime like during war, political crisis or absence of leadership. There are opinions that vary as to what the traits are and to what extent success can be predicted using those traits. Study has shown that even though some people can possess these traits natural, those who don't possess them can learn and have them built into his/her behaviour and thinking thereby affecting their leadership potential.

Going by modern day thought, leadership is seen as a skill to be mastered and so the above characteristics can be acquired. It is therefore paramount that these traits are known so that a leader can be worked on and made to acquire them in order to make great a leader.

The Contingency Theories

Contingency Theories & Situational Theories of Leadership

The contingency leadership theory also known as situational theory seeks meaning in the background of a leader. It checks for the impact of the success or failure of a leader. The effectiveness of a leader is determined by background of that leader. The most important aspect of a leader is the context and not his or her personality. This theory suggests that leadership style to be adopted depends on the situation in consideration and so it takes a particular leadership style that has been proven to have yielded result and suggests that good leaders that want to suggest should emulate that same leadership style while considering at the same time adopt the variable that made the leader successful. It believes that the right leader should be subject to the situation at hand. Therefore it determines the best style of leadership best suited for a given situation.

Renowned leadership researchers Hodgson and White believe that the best form of leadership is one that finds the perfect balance between behaviors, needs, and context. Good leaders do not only possess the right qualities but they're also able to analyze their followers' needs and the situation at hand. In a nutshell, the contingency theory suggests that great leadership is a combination of many key variables. Contingency theory has huge advantages which includes that leaders are able to be effective irrespective of their situation. There are criticism about this theory which suggests that there's no much context that goes into the context of the situation, it focuses on the importance of the situation without considering the psychology of the employees or even the company and also do not bother about changes that may occur in the leadership style over time. There are internal factors that impact on the leader and the situation e.g. the type of organization, the size of the team, the leadership style and the external factor like the market place and customer's feelings. Situations like this play a significant role in the leadership style.

There are five types of contingency theories thus; Fielders model, Hersey and Blanchard's situational theory, leader member exchange theory, path goal theory, leader participation model.

Fiedler's Contingency Theory

Fred Fiedler was an Austrian-born American psychologist who was involved in industrial and organizational psychology. From his research, he found that personalities alone could not effectively help pick a leader. He realized that the situation in which a leader was, greatly determined his success. He referred to the leader's personality as the 'leadership style' and the situation as the 'situational favorableness.'

To identify a suitable leader for a given situation, these two aspects would have to be considered. For the leadership style, Fiedler came up with a scale he called the Least Preferred Co-Worker (LPC) scale. This scale considers several traits of co-workers a leader would not want to work with - the persons a leader feels would make it difficult to succeed if worked with.

Hersey-Blanchard Situational Leadership Theory:

This is also referred to as the situational leadership model. It is mainly determined by the level of maturity of your followers. The maturity level of your followers is determined by their task skills and motivation.

Task skills – this is the ability for followers to complete tasks using the skills they have.

If their task skills are low, then you will have to impart some knowledge into them.

Motivation – this is a measure of the amount of enthusiasm followers have for finishing

tasks. If their motivation is high, then the leader will not have much work trying to

convince them of the importance of staying on course. On the other hand, they could

be less motivated towards working. In such situations, a leader will have to put in some effort in order to ensure the whole team flows in unity. Motivation and Task skills are used to form four distinct levels of readiness for the work.

Path-Goal Theory

This theory looks at the leader's style but puts emphasis on the results coming from the followers. The leader is viewed more like a source of inspiration who can influence his followers to complete the job. The theory was introduced by Martin G. Evans (1970) and further developed by Robert House (1971).

This theory is based on the expectancy theory by Victor Vroom (1964) which essentially states that people always act according to the reward expected. If they believe that what they are told to do will pay off, and the reward is something they value, then they will put in the effort.

Vroom–Yetton Contingency Model

This is also referred to as the decision-making model. Decision making is key in leadership and to a large extent, determines the relations between the leader and the followers. This relation has an impact on the leader's success.

Leaders make decisions differently. Yet, being a contingency theory, situations still have a lot of influence over how a leader makes decisions.

This theory differentiates between five types of leadership styles. They are primarily three but two have two degrees to which they can be implemented.

- **Autocratic (A1)** – a completely autocratic style of leadership is used in making decisions. Whatever information has become enough to make the decision and no further input from the team is required.

- **Autocratic (A2)** – this is still autocratic but not as extreme as the previous style. Some consultation is done with team members so as to obtain more information as needed. Afterwards, the leader makes the decision alone.
- **Consultative (C1)** – the leader consults with team members individually so as to get their opinions. Then he proceeds to make the decision by himself.
- **Consultative (C2)** – the consultations in this style of leadership are at a wider level. The leader organizes a meeting for all team members, or as many as possible, so as to discuss the situation. He/she gets their suggestions but still makes the decision.
- **Collaborative (G2)** – this style is purely focused on reaching a consensus. The leader organizes for a meeting to discuss the situation. He facilitates the discussion and urge everyone to give their suggestion. The decision is then made together based on the consensus of the team. To make the decision, some factors also come up as important considerations. These are:

Quality of the decision – the quality of the decision to be made is key in determining the process you will follow. For example, critical business decisions require a lot of information to be available. This could mean lots of consultations.

A team's commitment – the degree of commitment a team has is also a major factor to consider. The more invested people are into the leader and the business, the more the decisions made will affect them.

Vroom and Yetton developed a decision tree to help illustrate the process of decision making.

Figure 3.5 - Vroom-Yetton decision tree.

- i. Assess the suitability of one of the leadership theory that you have analysed in the context of your organization's international plans. The analysis should include a careful consideration and justification of the factors determining the chosen leadership style.
- ii.

STARBUCKS INTERNATIONAL PLANS AND GROWTH STRATEGY

Contingency/Situational theory of Leadership is best suited for the international plans for expansion. Expanding to a foreign land where Starbucks will be starting operation new needs a very careful and thorough analysis of the recruitment, sorting of employees that can do what in order to achieve the set task, analyze the environment and take decision according to what is workable in that given

situation and so the contingency leadership theory will be suitable in order to achieve its goal accordingly.

The new terrain is situational and so requires situational approach of leadership as described below;

Contingency Leadership Theory: Providing Leadership through Flexibility

The situation leadership theory stands on the premise that no particular style of leadership is the best rather it's all about the type of leadership and strategies are best suited for the given task and so this story suggests that the most effective leaders are those who have the ability to adapt their style to the situation and take on the task, the nature of the group and other factors that can contribute the achievement of the set goal.

This theory often referred to as," Hersey-Blanchard Situational Leadership Theory named after its developers, Dr. Paul Hersey, author of "The Situational Leadership and Kenneth Blanchard, author of "One-Minute Manager."

Leadership Styles

Dr.Paul Hersey and Kenneth Blanchard suggest that leadership has four primary styles:

Telling (Q1): The leader tells subordinate/followers what to do and how to do it.This style is used to direct followers with low competence but high commitment.

Selling (Q2): This leadership style involves though follow up by leaders on their subordinate/followers. Leaders try to get their followers to buy into their ideas. This style is used to oversee followers with some competence but low commitment.

Participating (Q3): The leader allows members of the group to be more proactive in coming up with ideas and making decisions with less direction. This style is used to oversee followers with high competence but variable commitment.

Delegating (Q4): This style is otherwise known as hands-off leadership style where the leader allows the group members to come with ideas, take decisions and take responsibility. This style is basically used to oversee followers with high competence and high commitment.

Developmental Levels

The developmental level of followers regarding their knowledge and competence is key in determining the right leadership style to use in any given situation.

Hersey and Blanchard's theory identifies four different levels of maturity as follows;

- **D1:** low competence/high commitment.
- **D2:** Some competence/low commitment.
- **D3:** High competence/variable commitment.
- **D4:** High competence/High Commitment.

Matching Styles and Levels

In order to get the best from employees and achieve success in any given task, developmental level needs to be matched with leadership style. The following leadership styles are the most appropriate for these developmental levels:

Developmental Level	Appropriate Leadership Style
D1 low competence/high commitment	S1 Telling

D2 Some competence/low commitment	S2 Selling
D3 High competence/variable commitment	S3 Participating
D4 High competence/High Commitment	S4 Delegating

Table 3.0 - Development level and leadership style

How this theory will work for Starbucks in a new Location

At the beginning of the project, the Telling style should be used when followers do not have defined responsibility or required knowledge about the task to be able to work on their own until the followers/subordinate becomes more knowledgeable and experienced then the leader may then move into delegating style depending on their different levels of development.

This contingency model of leadership works with flexibility so that leaders can easily adapt according to the situation and the need of their followers as it affects the task. This approach avoids failures that may suffice due to single style approach by knowing that there are different ways of tackling every given situation and that leaders are capable of evaluating a situation and the developmental levels of subordinates over time in order to determine the most appropriate/effective approach to use at a given situation.

This contingency theories considers the complexity of a situation and the roles many individuals are acting on who will eventually contribute to the outcome of the given task and so in the expansion plan of Starbucks to Nigeria ,Contingency model is highly recommended in this manner in order to successfully launch in the new location.

Contingency Leadership Style II

The Contingency Leadership Style II (or SLII model) was founded by Kenneth Blanchard and builds on Blanchard and Hersey's original theory. According to this version of the theory, effective leaders must base their attitude on the developmental level of the group members for specific tasks.

Competence and Commitment

The developmental level is determined by each individual's level of competence and commitment.

These levels include:

- **Fascinated beginner (D1):** High commitment, low competence.
- **Encouraged learner (D2):** Some competence, low commitment.
- **Resourceful (D3):** High competence/variable commitment.
- **Independent achiever (D4):** High competence/High Commitment.

SLII Leadership Styles

SLII proposes that effective leadership depends on two key attitudes: assisting and guiding. Directing attitudes which include specific directions and instructions as well as attempting to control the behavior of group members. Supporting behaviors include actions such as listening, encouraging subordinates, offering recognition and feedback.

Key Factors in determining the chosen contingency leadership theory for expansion plan to Nigeria.

After determining the employee and environmental variables then Starbucks should evaluate the leadership style to adopt for successful venture by analyzing the task. When evaluating this expansion task, there are four key factors that leaders must consider according to experts in determining the leadership style to adopt.

Consider the Relationship

Social and interpersonal factors can play a vital role in determining which leadership approach is best to adopt in this expansion plan. Leaders need to consider the relationship between the members of the group and the leader.

For instance, a group that does not have efficiency and productivity will most likely benefit from leadership style that emphasizes order, clarity of roles and rules while a group that a productive group that has highly skilled people will benefit from leadership style that is democratic where members are allowed to work independently as well as well as have input in organizational decision..

Consider the Task

The leader must consider the given task in this case, the expansion of Starbucks to Nigeria. This task can be simple or complex depending on how Starbucks evaluates the environment with an experience from similar task; the leader must have a clear idea of what the task is all about in order to determine the success level.

Consider the Level of Authority

The level of authority the leader has over group members should be considered critically. Power such as the capacity to fire, hire, reward, or reprimand subordinates given to a leader should be analyzed

in line with the type of leader assigned to handle the task. Some leaders gain power through relationships with employees, often by gaining respect from them, offering support to them, and helping them have ownership spirit by making them be part of decision making. This will guide in choosing the leadership style to adopt for this expansion.

Consider the Level of Development

The level of development of each individual group member need to be considered, the different level of development is a measure of the member's ability to complete a task as well as his/her willingness to complete a task. A clear recipe for failure is assigning a task to someone who has the willingness but does not have the ability to do it.

The ability to recognize each employee's level of development helps the leader to choose the best leadership approach that will assist employees accomplish their goals.

3© Discuss the behavioural dimensions that would be required in the management of human resources in the new foreign context of your organization. Specifically, your report should cover the following:

- (i) Identify some of the key challenges that you are likely to face in the international environment (from a human resources point of view such as understanding human behaviour, identifying employee needs)

4.0. HUMAN RESOURCES IN NIGERIA AND KEY CHALLENGES

Expansion from one country or region with a different geopolitical and sociocultural background poses several challenges. In a multicultural nation the effects are more pronounced, as later discussed an analysis of such a situation is multifaceted and research has proven that differences are more widely anticipated from person to person than collectively. Stereotyping a society mostly leads to failure as discovered by Letestu & Holmgren's (2012) thesis discovers.

In another dimension, it is clear that preparation and training for cross-cultural interactions are critical. In earlier discussions of the need for cultural sensitivity by expatriate managers, reports indicate that up to 40 per cent of expatriate managers end their foreign assignments early because of poor performance or an inability to adjust to the local environment. Moreover, about half of those who do remain function at a low level of efficiency. The indirect costs may be far greater, depending on the expatriate's position, Relations with the host-country government and customers may be damaged, resulting in a loss of market share and a poor reception for future PCNs. Both cross-cultural adjustment problems and practical differences in everyday living present challenges for expatriates and their families. Examples are evident from a survey of expatriates when they ranked the countries that presented the most challenging assignments to them, along with some pet peeves from their experiences. Even though cross-cultural training has proved to be effective, less than a third of expatriates are given such training. In a study by Harvey of 332 U.S. expatriates (dual-career couples), the respondents stated that their MNCs had not provided them with sufficient training or social support during the international assignment. Much of the rationale for this lack of training is an assumption that managerial skills and processes are universal. In a simplistic way, a manager's domestic track record is used as the major selection criterion for an overseas assignment. In most countries, however, the success of the expatriate is not left so much to chance. The demands on expatriate managers have always been as much a result of the multiple relationships that they have to maintain as they are of the differences in the host-country environment.

Cross-cultural Training in language and practical affairs is quite straightforward, but cross-cultural training is not; it is complex and deals with deep-rooted behaviors. The actual process of cross-cultural training should result in the expatriate learning both content and skills that will improve interactions with host-country individuals by reducing misunderstandings and inappropriate behaviours.

The goal of this training is to ease the adjustment to the new environment by reducing culture shock in a state of disorientation and anxiety about not knowing how to behave in an unfamiliar culture. The cause of culture shock is the trauma people experience in new and different cultures, where they lose the familiar signs and clues that they use to interact in daily life and where they must learn to cope with a vast array of new cultural clues. It is helpful to recognize the stages of culture shock to understand what is happening. Culture shock usually progresses through four stages honeymoon, irritation and hostility, gradual adjustment, biculturalism. Similar to culture shock, though usually less extreme, is the experience of subculture shock. This occurs when a manager is transferred to another part of the country where there are cultural differences essentially from what she or he perceives to be a "majority" culture to a "minority" one. The shock comes from feeling like an "immigrant" in one's own country and being unprepared for such differences. For instance, someone going from New York to Texas will experience considerable differences in attitudes and lifestyle between those two states just like in Nigeria that has both cultural issues and religious issues. These differences exist with cultures that range from roaming ranches and high technology to Bible-belt attitudes and laws and to areas with a mostly muslim or Christian heritage.

With the understanding of these key external factors,HRM mangers can make strategic decisions that will enhance the achievement of organizational goals.

Apart from cultural inflences,there are other challenges which are external fig 3c(i)which affects an organization and so needs attention in order for the manager to be able to find solution to the

challenges. Given the trend nowadays there are other in-depth external forces that HR manager must look it, analyse and find ways of solving them for an enhanced performance. These external forces are as shown in fig 3.6

Figure 3.6. - External forces Human resource managers must analyse

These are 7 main task HRM managers perform and they must consider if they must succeed.

STRATEGIES TO ATTRACT AND RECRUIT LOCAL TALENT

In order to get the best talent, Starbucks, has to deploy several strategies in order to recruit the right employees. Strategies such as:

To recruit, develop and retain talent are crucial to the success of every organization. The inevitable nature of international expansion need of some businesses has made this point very important and unavoidable and so in order to compete favourably, you will need to strategize on the best way to attract and recruit talent in an unfamiliar country. International HR managers know that it's very challenging recruiting employees abroad than from home because of the variations in related laws and customs by countries.

Considering recruiting local nationals (citizens of the host country) you have to strategize on the recruitment that will take cognizance of laws, culture and market practice of your target country.

This report focuses on crucial areas you should consider when developing the strategy in order to take care of ensuring you stay on the right side of the local laws and also to attract top talents for

Looking at Market for the 21st Century

Starbucks employers must understand the many dynamics for recruiting local talents, creative and evolving ways of recruiting talents. Just advertising for a position on the mainstream recruiting website would likely not reach out to the dream talent in your target country; you need to do much more than that for the right talent to be attracted.

People in most countries are using information from online such as LinkedIn and Glassdoor to search for jobs and employers also use similar tools to find suitable employees. Senior people are prone to being made to write reviews about their own experiences as part of the recruitment exercise. This strategy can be used in any country.

Knowledge of Local Culture

Even though every company has its own unique culture, some companies communicate their core culture more than others. For every that intends to establish and maintain its operations internationally should know that it should clearly state their core cultures clearly regarding what's acceptable or what is not. This will obviously enable its HR and other management team determines

how to best get that core culture adapted to in every country of operation which includes how to adapt to their recruitment practices so as to be able to align to company culture and local laws and customs. For instance, a company may value treating everyone equally irrespective of sex while some countries may treat theirs differently.

In a country like Saudi Arabia for instance, women are not allowed to drive under their local law. How would a company that wants to establish there and do not have such restrictions in its country handle this in their recruitment process?

In dealing with this, its pertinent to do proper etiquette interview in the country one is recruiting from in order to recruit the best.

For instance an interviewee is addressed as Mr or Mrs then followed by his/her surname while in Nigeria, they are better addressed without prefix just their first name or first and surname.

Local Recruiting Laws Compliance

It is critical to understand the local laws guiding recruitment in your target country; this will not only help in attracting the right talent but will make you avoid fines and lawsuits.

In a country like France, you must publish job description in French even though, translation can be made but the law requires that you must do that in French. With this in mind, a company will obviously tread with caution and if the job description is not well translated, it will be misleading and damaging and so it's crucial to bear in mind that job duties must portray the exact same thing in the target country as in the host country.

Many legal considerations need to be made when recruiting in another country, this includes considering local laws that governs protection of data e.g. in UK, the recruitment law only permits an employer to collect personal information and not irrelevant information like bank details and the personal information collected must be used for only recruitment. Failure to adhere to local laws can lead to not just fines but will likely damage the image of the company.

Supplementary Benefits and Allowances Knowledge

It's a known fact that bullying your competitors out of the recruiting race by offering higher salaries or allowances doesn't work anymore rather a company recruiting in a new country research and find out what salaries and incentives are available to advertised position and if possible set up a scheme that will address group benefits and salaries for better decision on how best to achieve a better remuneration package for the prospects depending on his/her environment.

Laws and customs vary from region to region like in a complex country like Nigeria with multi-cultural and multi religion operates by native laws and customs, federal laws as well as religious requirement too and so you need to understand the way they operate if you intend to expand to Nigeria.

Under Germany's social security regime that's so complex and complicated, it completely takes away the need for supplemental employer benefits meanwhile in the contrary employers provide additional benefits to supplement the state's flat-rate social security scheme

Understanding the way allowances are taxed is a very important approach that will guide HR on better way to recruit and retain employees.

It's always good to know the market average of certain benefits in order to ensure competitive compensation package during recruitment process.

In order to present your company as a culturally savvy employer, your HR need to understand the laws and customs that's related to recruiting in that target country. This will enable you maximize your advantage/edge when searching for local talent.

A Broader Job Vacancy

There is need for clarity in specifying the type of employee you are seeking in terms of profile, company history, pay scale, opportunities etc. This makes it possible for the right person to be attracted without waste of time.

At Starbucks smart recruitment provides a clear picture of every required description about the job notification. It also clearly communicates job requirements and how one can benefit from this profile. Starbucks stands out in the way their job vacancies are created by stating company's culture while at the same time mention how their employees have life-work balance and the perks they are entitled to. There are short video or a link to the company's career blog in job posts in order to express these plus points.

Campus recruiting

The colleges are full of young and dynamic talents who show immense enthusiasm in their work. A good percentage of workers at Starbucks employees are students. Under the philosophy of "none of us is as good as all of us," Starbucks is committed to being fair and conducting business, including talent attraction, in a manner that respects all people. They incorporate top technology, amazing employees, and key strategies to support diversity, inclusion, and equity throughout their talent processes.

Campus recruitment is a great way to recruit students and recent graduates. Some of the methods that are and can be deployed by Starbucks are:

- Getting featured in campus newspapers
- Conduct workshops and seminars in different colleges to showcase Starbucks and the career opportunities they have.
- Sponsoring college festivals and other cultural events
- Inviting students for an industry tour to learn about the Starbucks structure and functioning and have them interact with a few of the eminent stakeholders of Starbucks
- Offering internship programs where interested students can intern with Starbucks

- Having a different recruitment team for these freshers who themselves are young professionals and understand the budding minds

iii. Integrating cultural differences that results out of your internationalization plans and the organizational plans to respond to these challenges.

CHALLENGES IN THE NIGERIAN RESTAURANT INDUSTRY

Euromonitor (2018) in their country report claims that, Fast food restaurants are expected to grow over the forecast period, driven by urbanization and the increasingly rapid lifestyles of Nigerians, which encourages them to choose a quick fix for their meal requirements. This is especially so, given that the average age of Nigerian consumers is below 30 years. The same report declares economic stagnation as the negation of the progress of restaurant chains citing major chained fast food operators losing their value share in 2017 as consumers moved to cheaper options upon dwindling incomes. Previously quite successful brands were forced to close outlets, including Mr Bigg's and KFC, the international chicken fast food chain, as profitability dipped.

In another report, Oxford Business Group (OBG, 2020) analyses that despite the challenges inherent in retailing in Nigeria, the quick-service restaurants (QSR) segment had been growing rapidly. Like many areas of the economy, its long-term potential stands out in a global context because of Nigeria's sizeable population, currently standing at around 180 million. But while investors in most consumer-facing industries are expecting smaller returns upfront in exchange for bigger ones later on, QSR offers investors a quick turnaround for profits. The challenges, however, are familiar from other sectors, including the cost of electricity, land, experienced laborers and importing inputs. Challenges unique to QSR include striking a balance between the local palette and popular international tastes, all while maintaining consistency across franchise locations.

As of 2014 there were over 800 QSR outlets in Nigeria, the vast majority of them branded by about 100 small and medium-sized local companies, according to the Association of Fast Food and Confectioners of Nigeria (AFFCON). They generated about N200bn (\$1.22bn) in revenue and employed more than 500,000 workers, according to AFFCON's president, Bose Ayeni. What precisely constitutes a QSR business varies by source, however. Market research by the US Department of Commerce's Commercial Service found 290 QSR locations, for example, with three firms dominating the field: Mr. Bigg's, Tantalizers and Food Concepts, the parent company of Chicken Republic.

Some of the major challenges that will rear its head in the Nigerian market would include:

I. Understanding the Nigerian employee needs as opposed to the global employee needs. The high rate of unemployment in the country (23% of total workforce) creates an atmosphere where HR managers reduce employee incentives. International best practices are not followed in order to balance job performance and satisfaction.

II. Governmental policies are generally unstable most especially towards labour laws. International practices cannot always be followed as swerving policies can alter management protocols.

III. Religious and multicultural nature of the employees can create rifts in human resource management. For instance, Northern Nigeria is predominantly composed of Muslim population, dietary choices differ across religious lines and dressing and grooming and even choice of staff sex must be considered so as not to offset a religious or cultural crisis with the host community.

Furthermore, stereotyping a society mostly leads to failure as discovered by Letestu & Holmgren's (2012) thesis discovers. In another dimension, it is clear that preparation and training for cross-cultural interactions are critical. In earlier discussions of the need for cultural sensitivity by

expatriate managers, reports indicate that up to 40 percent of expatriate managers end their foreign assignments early because of poor performance or an inability to adjust to the local environment. Moreover, about half of those who do remain function at a low level of effectiveness. The indirect costs may be far greater, depending on the expatriate's position, Relations with the host-country government and customers may be damaged, resulting in a loss of market share and a poor reception for future PCNs. Both cross-cultural adjustment problems and practical differences in everyday living present challenges for expatriates and their families. Examples are evident from a survey of expatriates when they ranked the countries that presented the most challenging assignments to them, along with some pet peeves from their experiences. Even though cross-cultural training has proved to be effective, less than a third of expatriates are given such training. In a study by Harvey of 332 U.S. expatriates (dual-career couples), the respondents stated that their MNCs had not provided them with sufficient training or social support during the international assignment. Much of the rationale for this lack of training is an assumption that managerial skills and processes are universal. In a simplistic way, a manager's domestic track record is used as the major selection criterion for an overseas assignment. In most countries, however, the success of the expatriate is not left so much to chance. The demands on expatriate managers have always been as much a result of the multiple relationships that they have to maintain as they are of the differences in the host-country environment.

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STARBUCKS RESPONSE TO CHALLENGES IN NIGERIA

In their master's thesis, Letestu & Holmgren (2012) described certain companies that could not reach a market because its products are not culturally compatible to their proposed communities. This it is one of the entry barriers for Starbucks, certain cultures in Nigeria have religious or cultural disdain for certain food, and others prefer non fast foods. Fitting into such environment would require a professional study of Nigeria as a multicultural country. Culture plays a vital role the product. The lesser the cultural sensitivity the product has the independent it is from cultural influence and on the other hand the more sensitive it is to culture the more it influence the direction of an organization's process of internationalization. Hence it could be concludes that nature of the products which in

Starbucks refers to the food served plays a vital role on whether the culture has an influence on it or not during the internationalization. In this case, Nigeria which is segregated in terms of locations where there are extreme culture sensitivity and so Starbucks will have to study those areas with high acceptance of their product like Lagos and prepare to launch then first before expanding to other locations with the help of citizens who are already working in the company who sees herself as part of the business.

The difference in cultural perceptions and its consequence was one of the ground breaking observations of Letestu & Holmgren (2012) that quite repeatedly came up during the interviews in their research. It was interesting to note how conflicts can occur because of the similarities between cultures than the dissimilarities. The interviewees were taken by surprised how their initial perception of the specific culture that they are familiar with was wrong and quite opposite leading to conflicts than in an unfamiliar cultural environment. The most common observation is that when someone is faced with an unknown and unfamiliar cultural situation that person tends to be on high alert to prepare and cope with it than on perceived familiar grounds and be faced with unexpected cultural behavior. On the other hand in all the incidence discussed in empirical it could be seen that the interviewees were expected similar linear behavior in another liner country but experienced the opposite and triggered cultural conflicts that ended in disappointment and dissatisfied cultural experience. Hence all agreed that it was easier to deal with cultures expect to be different than in a culture that you already think that you are very familiar but not. Another interesting but related factor found in their finding is on stereotypical view of culture. Stating that “Everybody has stereotypical thinking of another culture, and it is naive to say that people don’t, but people should not stick to it”. The stereotypical cultural perception or prejudice against another culture and people in it also plays role in this matter. It was emphasized that it is very hard to find a person who does not have prejudice against another culture. Still they stated everybody should adopt and understand their business partners for who they are and not for where they come from.

The major reason that the above conflict occurred is because of the psychic distance each of these individuals had. As previously stated psychic distance is defined as the “The distance between the home market and a foreign market, resulting from the perception of both cultural and business differences.” - Evans & Mavondo (2002)

Thus it does not matter whether the cultures are perceived to be similar or different as every culture has subcultures and every individual is unique. The proposal and claim open here advocates for local ethnographic studies of the different regions where the company wants to open market. Any categorization contributes to regional cultural homogenization, it's true, but it is important to overcome different fallacies, as in this case the ecological fallacy: inferring the nature of individuals, for example, from the statistics added to the group where these individuals belong; This means supposing that all the individuals of the same social group share the common traits that define the group. It is important to overcome this to review and accept that: subcultures are influenced by a national culture but within a country there are intra - cultural differences. Each individual perceives and understands the culture of the society where they live in very different ways, and this is something that we should not ignore.

Taking into account all this cultural framework, a company can end up focusing on the aspects of labour relations, work modes, human resources policies. It is not only a job of adaptation of professionals settled in a new environment, or a good translation of languages, but it is a process so that companies and future workers can have the greatest possible understanding both for labour rights issues such as for negotiations, marketing programs, or production itself.

Starbuck's has potentially created more economic impact for diverse communities than any other company in the world. Starbucks believes are rooted in “Diversity IS Inclusion”, a bold and seismic value proposition where every individual feels their culture, identity, and experiences are valued and respected. Listening to and participating in knowledge-sharing and eclectic insights has helped the

organization to where they are today - from crew members to board members, from suppliers to customers to community partners.

By aligning “Diversity IS Inclusion” proposition with the culture pillars of Customer Obsessed, Better Together, and Committed to Lead, there is a purposeful affect to the community in a positive way.

Integrating into a community and integrating such culture into the global conglomerate involves being an active member in the communities Starbucks serves. This has been fundamental to the Starbucks’ business since the founding of the company. Starbucks, its franchisees and employees, continue to seek ways to make meaningful impacts on the diverse communities where they live and work. To that end, the Global Diversity, Inclusion & Community Engagement team of Starbucks has established shared value relationships with several community-based organizations. These relationships help provide direct insights into issues and challenges facing host communities - detailing relationship stance as neighbors or as business owners.

Some of the notable community based organizations that have worked and still work with Starbucks are graphically represented in figure 4.0.

Figure 4.0 - Logos of Companies and organizations that have worked and /or are still working with Starbucks

iv) Review and critically synthesize the various influences on behaviour in organisations and the interface with management in integrating and balancing these.

[5 marks]

CRITICAL REVIEW OF VARIOUS INFLUENCES ON BEHAVIOUR IN ORGANISATIONS AND MANAGEMENT INTERFACE IN INTEGRATING AND BALANCING THEM

Behaviour at work is influenced by some variables and dimensions. These are individual, the group, the organisation and the environment (Mullins 2016)

Figure 4.1 - Influences on employee behaviour

The individual

The attitude/behaviors of individuals in any given situation impacts on the organization. If these behaviors are positive, they will impact positively on the organization which will lead to enhanced

performance and ultimately lead to achievement of the organization objectives but if it's negative, it will lead to conflict, damage and issues on the misbehavior at workplace.

The group

In all workplaces, there are always teams/group who are very important for the general performance and effectiveness of an organization. Group pressure formed from individual co-existence exerts influences on each other and this can have significant influence on the behavior of employee.

The organization

The ways individuals and group interact can be highly influence by the formal structure of an organization. Their processes are guided by technology, management patterns and leadership which in turn has direct influence on individuals and teams in performing their activities to ensure the achievement of organization's objectives

The environment

The external environment which consists of organization and the people who work for them and every decision or behavior by these people affects the organization, like through enhancement in technology, changes in law, political instability, globalization. The increased demand on the adaptability of an organization is brought about by the increased pace of change within the external environment.

Integrating and Balancing the Variables That Influence Behaviour At Work.

Some variables influence an employee's behavior and so it's very important that managers guide their group members to behave well at their workplace. In order to develop a positive attitude/behaviors employees should be made to feel important at their workplace in order to develop a positive behavior, have sense of responsibility and passion for the work.

Hard work of employees must be encouraged: Its very important and paramount to acknowledge employees efforts especially in the presence of their colleagues for motivation and enhanced performance. They will not only feel good with the organization but go extra mile to get others to believe in the organization which will make them perform better in their given task whether individually or in group. Always give them feedback whenever there is need to do so. Its very important to notice every positive impact by any employee. This brings about loyalty. They need to be rewarded from time to time and it's important to value every contribution made by each individual.

Ensure no employee is overburdened: The duties and task of every employee is according to specialization, expertise. Confusion sets in when the respective job roles/functions is mismatched which in most cases leads to lose of interest in the job. When this happens, employees just waste their time in the office browsing, chatting and all other unproductive tasks

Awareness of rules and regulations of organization: Employees should be made to understand what is expected of him and most importantly read out the rules and regulation that guides employees behavior in the workplace. There are acceptable ways to behave in the workplace and every employee is made to understand that. Punctuality is key.

Under performance should not be mocked at: Criticism over underperformed task by an individual should be discouraged otherwise it will make the employee demotivated and low in spirit. This need to be dealt with wisdom. Try to find out politely why the under performance and what the

possible solution can be. Never shout at a subordinate. Discover what additional skills that can assist them with their task. Never talk to them in public because it can make them not to discuss their problems in future thereby hiding their problems. Show them care.

Regular monitoring of employees performances: Managers need to show seriousness so that their team members will also show seriousness in carrying out their assignment for achievement of result. Dont present the image of the organization badly or even the client in the presence of employees. Pry into the employee's lives and try to advise where necessary. Be an interactive leader. This makes them feel fulfilled and open.

Allow decision making: Give the employees some sense of responsibility by allowing them take some decisions. Dont interfere much in their affair.

Encourage freedom of speech: among colleagues and stakeholders. They should be allowed to express their views and thoughts.employees need to have freedom of expression. Let them speak and express their views and opinions. They need to have a say in organization's major decisions.

3d) Analysis of best practices in IHRM. Specifically, you should:

Analyse other organizations belonging to similar industry for their international HRM best practices, with a special focus on compensation and performance management of expatriate employees.

[10 marks]

STARBUCKS, COMPETITION AND THEIR HRM PRACTICES

Starbucks advantage over its competitors is the ability to manage their workforce efficiently. All the employees are considered partners in Starbucks and are provided with training programs for better understanding of the product and for acquiring the techniques and skills that they will be required to perform their tasks.

Starbucks compensation is very high in order to keep qualified employees.

Compensation: This is the financial and non-financial obligation by an organization to reward its employees for work well done. Employees in Starbucks participate in various form of reward for those that do full time or part time work.

Starbucks employees' total package includes the following depending on job and situation.

- Paid time off
- Competitive pay
- Bonuses
- Insurance medical life
- Retirement savings plan
- Discounted stock purchase plan and stock option
- Financial Aid (emergency)
- A free pound of coffee weekly

Performance Management of Starbucks expatriate employees

This is an integral part of an organization. The organization set up criteria which they will use to evaluate the performance of their employee in a given task. It's more or less a yardstick of measurement for the evaluation of how the employee is performing.

STARBUCKS COMPETITION AND THEIR HRM PRACTICES

McDonald's

McDonald's started as a burger brand in 1948 in San Bernardino, California. The company has been looking for a growth strategy for a very long time. With over 38,000 restaurants in over 120 countries in the world today they maintain the top position in the fast-food industry for the past 50 years.

Business strategy of McDonald's for employment planning is organized in the way so it can be sure that it has the correct figure of skilled individuals on the exact positions and at the right time. Nevertheless, they hire unskilled individuals, whose employment contracts are mostly on a short term basis, and try to train them to let them understand the objectives of the organization. With the help of the training strategy, McDonald's improves and develops the skills of the workers in the organization and provides promotions to retain employees.

On the financial side, McDonald's uses direct shares, uniforms, paid vacation, bonus scheme and stock purchase plan, competitive wages, MAC Card, Haircut Discounts, wages increases and so on to attract employees.

McDonald's is a big restaurant with so many branches around the world that it helps to reduce the unemployment around us. It promises a good future development chance for their employees.

Kentucky Fried Chicken

Kentucky Fried Chicken was founded in 1932 and nowadays is the largest fast-food chicken operator, and franchisor in the world. KFC has been proven to be a successful business enterprise with more than 11,000 restaurants in 109 countries around the world. HRM is valued there, as the company knows that its employees are at the center of their success.

During the late 1990s, KFC launched a new employee incentive program as part of a three million dollar reorganization of its corporate field operations. The program was intended to show general managers that they play an essential role in the success or failure of the company. The managers were taken to the corporate headquarters for three days of meetings and seminars. The company believed that a great way to develop great teams was to focus on restaurant leaders. The changes stemmed from a survey that was conducted and revealed that managers wanted more support from corporate headquarters, “they want to know that they are valued” (KFC initiates).

At KFC, all employees receive initial training, which covers food safety, business familiarization and online testing. The training is web-based in virtual reality classrooms where future employees are prepared. After commencing employment, team members continue their training through a program called CHAMPS.

HR PHILOSOPHY of KFC stands on “the CHAMPS program” i.e.

- C – Cleanliness
- H – Hospitality
- A – Accuracy
- M – Maintenance
- P – Product Quality
- S – Speed of Service

By means of structured employee training and effective retention strategies, the company can deliver a more consistent customer experience. The training, development, and retention of the right people are the key ingredients to the secret recipe that result in the long-term success of KFC

Burger King and IHRM Practices

Burger King is the world's 2nd largest food chain famous for serving delicious Burgers/Hamburgers across the world. The food chain employed around 35000 plus employees worldwide to serve millions of customers throughout its 17,796 location.

With so huge staff, it is not easy to keep them happy and loyal to the company. So, the company is offering Burger King Employee Benefits Program for its staff. Burger King Employee Benefits helps the staff to ensure a steady source of income with various types of savings plans.

Burger King's food chain offers the following benefits and perks that Burger King staff could enjoy: Burger King Health Insurance, Dental Insurance, Occupational Accident and Life Insurance, Long-term Disability Insurance, Paid Time off, free Drinks/Coke/Juice, & Paid Sick Leave 401 (k) plan and Performance-based bonuses, Flexible Hours, Employee Discount, Job Training, and Tuition Assistance.

Recruitment Process At Burger King

Recruitment process in this company involves: Applying online with a mini essay telling human resource why Burger King is the right place for the employee. Upon careful consideration by HR agree an invite is extended for a chat.

If that goes well, a face-to-face interview, where HR will find out more about the employee. It's also an opportunity for the employee to meet the BK team. Next referees are checked and a job is offered.

Upon acceptance the on-boarding and induction process as a brand new member of the BK team is initiated.

Although this process is quite cumbersome and requires a large HR work force for in-person interviews, this seems to be the novel way of interacting with employees. Recently, Burger King corp. has been given the annual Best People Practices Award for Leadership and Excellence in Workforce Practices in the quick-service category. The recognition was presented by People Report, a provider of human resources insight for the service sector industry. During the presentation, Burger King was touted for its achievements in management retention, hourly employee retention and composite diversity, year-over-year improvements, community involvement and overall sustainable business practices.

"We are honored to be recognized by People Report with their prestigious Best People Practices award," said Jose Tomás, executive vice president, chief human resources and communications officer for BKC. "We work hard to enhance, evolve and sustain our human resources practices throughout our organization."

Burger King Corp. is the largest QSR brand to win the award. It was recognized among the 100-plus companies that track and report their human capital intelligence monthly. The award was announced Nov. 17, not long after the company shuffled its senior management team after its sale to Brazilian company 3G Capital.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Human resources management plays very crucial role in the management of employees in order to work effectively and productively in order to always be above competition.

Borrowing a leaf from Burger king and their style of human resource management we could see an easy door to the solution of the HR problems riddled with Internationalization of a multinational company such as Starbucks. A close knit culture of Human resource management that involves a more employee oriented approach to recruitment. This would in turn enable a facilitation of the internationalization process as it becomes easier to analyze the needs of the human resource and the position they could fit perfectly in the team.

However, when moving into a multinational setup, it is quite pertinent to note that advanced preparation is needed by the management with a word of caution on stereotyping. Care should be taken to engage human resource practices which are not offensive to the host society or culture, acknowledging the fact that human resource practices should not be a 'one size fit all' affair.

Such a change would affect the global concept of diversity and unification to the restaurant giant. Different regions would incorporate differing human resource management practice. For instance the stricter culture in Europe and Asia that involves accuracy and speed would not be necessary in the African culture of patience.

Such a complicated structure of human resource management would incur a heavy cost to set-up and may disrupt supply chain and legal framework. But the benefit of acceptance by other culture both by the employees and by customers would in the long run outweigh the costs. The HRM practices

has helped Starbucks, McDonald and KFC to achieve their long term success significantly,therefore financial and human resources as well as time are mobilized for the maintenance of employees and talents .HRM practices help McDonald's, KFC and Starbucks to ensure their long-term success, development, improvement and expansion on the world market, hence the great amount of time, financial and human resources are mobilized for maintaining employees and talents

REFERENCES

Reference

- 2006. Starbucks taps into Taiwan coffee culture with new RTD offer. *Media: Asia's Media & Marketing Newspaper*: 11-11.
- Davis, R. 2008. The people vs Starbucks. *New Internationalist*(410): 21-23.
- Han, G. & Zhang, A. 2009. Starbucks is forbidden in the Forbidden City: Blog, circuit of culture and informal public relations campaign in China. *Public Relations Review*, 35(4): 395-401.
- Hoppe, M. H. 2004. Introduction: Greet Hofstede's culture's consequences: International differences in work-related values. An interview with Greet Hofstede. *Academy of management Executive*, 18(1), 73-79
- Izberk-Bilgin, E. 2008. When Starbucks Meets Turkish Coffee: Cultural Imperialism and Islamism as 'Other' Discourses of Consumer Resistance. *Advances in Consumer Research - North American Conference Proceedings*, 35: 808-809.
- Jennifer Weiner, T. P. I. Seattle-Based Starbucks Launches Arts, Culture Magazine.
- Keaten, J. 2003. Starbucks to break into France's cafe culture with first Paris store. *Marketing News*, 37(22): 48-48.

Reference

2. Klein, D. S. 2010. Brewing up a turnaround: HOW HOWARD SCHULTZ REVAMPED STARBUCKS. *Smart Business Tampa Bay*, 4(8): 10-10.
3. Maranhão, C. & de Pádua Carrieri, A. 2007. Tribal Knowledge: Business Wisdom Brewed from the Grounds of Starbucks Corporate Culture. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 10(3): 213-215.
4. Schneider, S., & Barsoux, J, 1997, Cultural and organization Managing Across Cultures, London, Prentice-Hall
5. Pellet, L. 2010. Shaping Corporate Culture of the Future: Companies that Inspire and Understand How Cultural Fit is the Path to Profits, Passion, and Purpose. *Journal of Corporate Recruiting Leadership*, 5(6): 16-22.
6. Joseph Michelli, 2006. The Starbucks Experience: 5 Principles for Turning Ordinary, McGraw-Hill
7. 陳穎. 星巴克品牌形象與消費者生活型態之自我一致性研究. 國立臺北教育大學, 台北市.
8. 蘇修賢. 2007. 以系統思考探討組織文化中價值體系所造成之成長限制: 以統一星巴克股份有限公司為例. 國立中山大學, 高雄市.